

Fully inhabiting the body to 'just be': The trajectory of a schizophrenic patient

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This paper originates from clinical work and is aimed at illustrating how a patient diagnosed with a specific type of schizophrenia was likely to accept/deny her condition. We chose to follow her, through verbal and bodily expressions, to try and understand how her fears, her deep anguish, and her difficulty to live could be treated. The patient was eventually able to build her own mixed environment (psychiatric and normal) partly because of establishing new relationships with individuals who really talk to her. To conclude, self-expression through the arts was found to be the main trajectory that helped us support her in her quest for an acceptable life despite a daily fight to survive.

Keywords: bodily expressions; environment; psychotic disorder; schizophrenia; self-expression

Based on clinical work and using specific patients likely to suffer from a mental health disorder as a background, the purpose of this article is to reflect on the space existing between patients' passive and active reactions when confronted by any type of background, while avoiding the act of 'entering' a sort of resonance. This dialectic is discussed in the present paper, against the general background of psychic suffering, which can affect the narcissistic foundations of patients' identity to the point of not allowing individuals to inhabit their body psychically, somatically, and cognitively. The variables of vulnerability and trauma are therefore introduced as elements that can influence people's ability to fully inhabit their bodies in the presence of psychopathology. First of all, the primary goal of this article will be to understand the trajectory of those patients who can progressively conquer their subjectivity through the appropriation of their body, while desiring and accepting to be permeated by their fantasy of experiencing anguish. Secondly, an attempt will be carried out to explore a schizophrenic patient's effort to structure her body, psyche, and reasoning mind in mutual and integrative ways.

It has been observed in our clinical practice that some patients decide to withdraw from certain environments (e.g., family and work) in which they are no longer likely to find warmth, a listening ear, a welcoming attitude, or a sense of confirmation of who they are; namely a kind of strengthening of their self-esteem. Therefore, relying upon Erikson's (1972) theory of psychosocial development, it can be assumed that patients are willing to take the risk of sharing an intimate part of themselves with other individuals whom they trust, with the final objective of getting to know and assessing themselves, therefore consolidating the autonomy of their subjectivity. Only by unveiling this part of themselves they can avoid to entirely conform to what social norms expect from them. They will, instead, seek to establish their own values to align with what they think they really are, or at least with what they want to be (dialectic between the self and the ideal of the self), while at the same time making compromises in their relationship with other human beings. However, individuals may also experience a bond in which they do not feel understood yet rather manipulated, and in which their subjectivity is denied. Therefore, they might lose faith in the other person and even doubt their own ability to simply just be; they may also feel ashamed for not being of interest to other human beings.

This is reminiscent of the adolescence years: what happens in adolescence when psychic autonomy is not there yet? In particular, if patients have never seen or felt any sort of validation by the external environment whenever they attempted to share personal information, what could this have triggered? Or again, when interactions first took place, when the young and immature individual was confronted by an environment that did not contain them enough? In other words, which consequences could be observed when an environment that not offered them enough narcissistic elements to take risks in life yet without risking their life, and that did not send back any structured messages (such as, for instance, the impotence to be psychically present)?

While growing up and going through moments of great vulnerability, some of these patients may be swallowed up by sectarian groups, or seduced by radical ideas leading them to believe in their megalomaniacal power to survive any harmful attacks. Some may try to protect themselves by withdrawing from the social scene, which usually offers a plurality of relationships. However, they never reach an illusory completeness and may even try to annihilate themselves, having failed to live for themselves, while life appears devoid of interest to them. They finally end up living without being able to inject meaning their life.

On the basis of this premise, observations will be presented in this article that were mainly recorded when meeting patients who had felt an inner lack of consistency during interactions happening in varied environments, from the nearest to them (the family) to the furthest. Some instances of withdrawal from the ordinary social world, gathered from patients' feelings and statements, will also be illustrated.

At the outset a feeling of social uselessness to the point of questioning the meaning of one's very own existence can be noted, and the individual is even doubtful about continuing to live on. One probes one's own place in this world, perceived as devoid of purpose, superfluous, insignificant. To explore this issue even further, the useful or useless scope of this insignificance is questioned. What are patients expressing in this instance, if not their struggle to just be themselves, together with a cry for help, directed inwards and outwards, just to find a way to stop sinking?

A feeling of rejection can also be observed to the point of wanting to isolate oneself, to become as 'small' as possible to avoid enduring an undervaluing, contemptuous, pitiful look from others. Feelings of shame can therefore be summoned, and patients can choose to live away from the world, in the shadow, to make themselves small and disappear, rather than risk being perceived in a dishonourable way. There exists the perception of being invisible to the point of not feeling perceived, heard, seen; this can consequently lead individuals to deter their dynamic thought performance. The road to perception before reaching elaboration is therefore hindered.

There is also the issue of no longer being able to find any values that are significant and meaningful enough to build a solid common foundation, as this is weakened by a loss of trust in those principles. How can human beings find ideals that resonate with their core selves, and that push them to exceed themselves, to once again

feel that they exist in true harmony with their fellow citizens, and that they are therefore neither wrong nor likely to live in a wrong way? The answer at this question is not so evident.

It is possible to observe a space to live in-between what is true and what is false, between the power to actively act according to one's choices, however limited these may be, and the authority to passively operate according to external desires and rulings.

All of the aforementioned situations, far from being exhaustive, are meant to introduce the key concept of this article, which states that being right with respect to relationships with other human beings and with oneself, can lead the individual to experience a certain number of risky situations, whose consequences are far from being negligible. The aim of this paper is hence to reflect on this issue, in particular when considering patients affected by mental pathologies such as melancholy.

This paper builds on the authors' previous work focused on the ability to *just be* in the real world, whose key objective was to show that a real interaction is possible when a confrontation with the others takes place and when there is space for movement. Being a psychologist also means accepting to be distressed by a typology of patients suffering from this type of psychic pain; this discomfort can only be implicit when trying to understand it in terms of what is felt, as well as in terms of what patients project onto therapists and what these can in turn project onto their clients from a cognitive and relational point of view, if anything simply because they are moved by empathy towards them.

However, before moving in unexplored territory, it is necessary to focus on the meaning of the concept behind 'being true'. One can think of this term, 'being true', in relation to the self as defined by Winnicott (1971), and also reflect on the meaning of the related idea known as 'position of being' (also known as the illusion of being). According to Winnicott's (1971) writings, in the process of 'being true' the very young child builds their sense of self through a proximal relationship with the mother-environment: this offers an image back to them. The quality of that image varies from being very rewarding to extremely resentful. Consequently, the child builds themselves in the eyes of the mother-environment. This look can be constructing or, conversely, deconstructing; in other words, it can send back to the child an image that will result in feelings such as being lovable enough or insufficiently beautiful and valued, even ugly and bad in extreme cases, yet always in accordance with parental projections.

Sometimes the very young child manages to preserve themselves by prematurely differentiating and overinvesting in knowledge, using the intellect to enhance a self-promoting self. In this specific moment of childhood, the young person does not yet have to manifest themselves as a subject in their own right. However, they would not always be protected if the parental figure they have introjected were to disappear in real life.

This hypothesis is based on the understanding of the psychological functioning of suicidal patients likely to suffer simply because they are alive and who, at some point in their life (experienced as vulgar and useless), usually give up. They finally lose their fear of letting go, leaving all their solitude behind. It is true that this feeling of solitude is remarkable and belongs to them and only them. They cannot share it. It is precisely this inability of sharing which they experience on a daily basis, placing in front position the early trauma caused by a failure to hang on and then followed by a life in disagreement with their environment, even though this is often beautiful, good, solid, and structured.

For suicidal patients, all attempts to cling onto something have failed. The metaphor of blood loss draining these individuals of their psychic energy can very well be deployed. Their need to take a break from the social scene is understandable. It enables them to close an internal breach. This fissure allows patients to face the matter of no longer existing in the wish of other human beings, taking advantage of finally feeling liberated from existing storming anxieties, however empty these may be; their bodies can no longer protect them from internal and external attacks. However, some of these individuals, cut off from the social scene, glued to their psychic wanderings without limits, can fall into the odd world of psychosis, thus protected from the danger of their whole being. In his superb interpretation of Freudian writings Jean-Claude Rolland speaks of desistence (*désêtre*). The desistence is a state that allows some patients who have built up a precarious subjectivity to endure their grief for being someone (Konrad, 2012).

The close environment, mainly composed of family members and caregivers, can no longer keep them alive, yet maintains an available space and place because it is always there for these individuals, always trying to offer them a warm and caring ear that embraces cognitive and relational empathy (Tisseron, 2011).

Living as a dead being who is alive, or as a living being who is going to die? The story of Solange

The above observations are reflected in the story of a patient who suffered from this inability to live and who, at the same time, depended on the death of loved ones and on people less close to her, to the point of preferring to live as a dead being who was still alive rather than as a living being who was anyway going to die. This adult

patient is here fictionally called Solange. Solange was affected by a mental pathology (schizophrenia), yet never ceased to act like everyone else to socially fit in, at the same time hoping to no longer feel isolated, or worse excluded from interactions with other people, and from oneself. One could describe this situation as a silent wish to deny the presence of mental illness.

Solange used to believe she was destined to have a career as a linguist. She attempted suicide several times: once to distance herself from her older sister who had suffered from an obsessive pathology that had captured parental attention, especially that of the mother. Solange's second suicide attempt happened after her own sister death: this had killed herself after calling Solange on the phone demanding help, while Solange was abroad. A third suicidal attempt took place after her mother prematurely died of cancer. Solange was hospitalised various times, took several medications whose dosage varied depending on the onset of the pathology, the reappearance of some of her symptoms or when she felt an uncontrollable pulsion to end her life.

This happened to be the case, even though rather insidiously, when she read an official consent document to participate to an experimental protocol for the treatment of severe depression, and instead discovered that she could contribute to the study because of her schizophrenia. She had originally thought to suffer from deep chronic depression, a pathology always and irreversibly attached to her core being; she had hoped to get rid of it by benefiting from this research study's results. She had longed to lose weight and pain at the same time to feel more relieved, freer, and certainly more independent. These thoughts were very common at the time of therapy, when she was sharing her private life with a woman. Her companion loved to travel and had managed to convince Solange to follow her around the world, even though Solange's body was often in pain; in fact, she had returned from one of these journeys away from her native France with an even more injured body.

Solange was unable to reach the second and last travel destination, as far away as the first one, because of a decompensation episode following her participation to the aforementioned research study; this, in theory, should have helped her heal. A conflict had however insinuated itself into her psyche without warning, her body had completely escaped, no longer operating the mediator function between her moods, emotions and her reasoning. A kind of abortion of her emerging *self* had instead taken place, sending it to another destination where delirium could freely express itself, outside the reality field of ordinary people.

Her reflection about the impossibility to heal her melancholy was ongoing. This was mixed to her desire to accept her dead relatives and a yearning to abandon them. Such ambivalence was visible in the various bodily pains afflicting her, yet also enlivening her. She used to talk about the rootlessness of her discomforts, at the same time evoking the quavering of her own *self*; this did not allow the consolidation of her narcissism, which decidedly remained too fragile for the birth of a *self*. A kind of perennial psychic viscosity was revealed to conscience. Consequently, a light was projected onto her dead relatives, constantly turned on. One could not help but think of the lights, metaphors of the soul, shining on all the dead people nourished and kept alive by this patient, like a shadow constantly edging her.

This therapeutic consideration was reached by observing the various preparations she undertook using the therapist as a passive helper; others would probably describe the therapist as an accomplice because of her consent to collaborate. Undeniably, and for a certain number of years, clinical work had been carried out to redevelop her environment. This could be observed through a gradual distancing from the workshops and the group mediations proposed by the psychiatric clinics. She had also managed to change psychiatrist by consulting a new one affiliated to a practice in the city and not in a psychiatric hospital environment. As a result, this had opened up new meeting spaces away from the ones already familiar to her.

This therapeutic distancing work was carried out together with the development of her creative capacity transposed to the field of verbal expression. This patient had studied linguistics and language, areas in which her mother had excelled, too. Having become a poet, she was particularly fond of a foreign poet whom her late sister had adored, too. At the time of therapy she attended creative writing workshops, participated in poetry competitions, won several awards and published collections of poems.

After a period of physical suffering, in which her body appeared to be waking up and agreed to being stimulated in some way, Solange learnt to take better care of it. Through physical movements she even accepted to move again, to be pushed around, and partly because she felt supported by her therapist. She started trusting the various practitioners who looked after her body, a nutritionist, an energy specialist and an osteopath. She tried at all costs to feel her body, to delineate it, because she had in the past felt alien to it, not knowing what to do with it.

Her body, which used to work as her warm and comfortable surrogate mother, sometimes also serving the functions of her deceased sister, of her previous lovers, and then of all those lovers who had not loved but only used her, made her look more like a round, fluffy doll moulding the shape of the person inhabiting it. This lasted for some time, the time necessary to sink, to feel let down by some people, yet refusing to be

destabilised, without any doubts too fragile and perhaps also resenting the fear of being 'contaminated' by pathology, yet supported by others.

Little by little, Solange was able to create a holding and handling environment; according to Winnicott (1971) the holding environment is a developmental stage in which the child and mother are one entity, as yet undifferentiated in the infant's consciousness. Moreover, at the same time she was being psychologically supported to sustain the process of building-up her real self and of legitimising her existence despite the death of family members to whom she had devoted her whole existence, almost as if living in their shadow.

Her will to live had always rubbed shoulders with the daily wish to die leaving no offspring. For a long time, she had wanted a child but had never been sustained in this sense. Nowadays, she continues her peregrinations in an environment that sends back a more rewarding image of herself. The doubts are still very present in her therapist's mind and she still refuses to accept her pathology. However, she manages to express this limitation by feeling ashamed of the fact that she cannot live for herself. She still lives to support her father, an individual who occupies a crucial place in her current environment, and with whom she shares the losses. Both her father and her therapist know that she continues to come to the clinic to avoid feeling isolated and disarmed in case her father dies.

To conclude, Solange was able to find a way to raise herself to the rank of *subject*, differentiating from the others by becoming, this time, a prisoner of her own writings. She chose to express herself through poetry, a creative exercise which was in itself part of immutability, even if this has only recently become clear to her. She managed to excel in this field, which has become hers and only hers, and she tries to shield it at all costs especially from her friends suffering from a mental illness like her. This behavior re-affirms her constant attempts to evade the gazes of her mother and sister, who in the past had even read her diary without her knowledge. Solange remembers having to hide it under her bed, the only place that really belonged to her, that allowed her to write and preserve her reasoning skills, her mental health.

By playing an explicit role, her feelings of being insignificant to others whom she valued more treasured than her were counterbalanced by this ability to get involved in a specific activity. However, this investment had to be prevented from becoming an overinvestment to cover-up a void in her internal life. In other words, as it often happens in some patients at some specific point in their healing journey, they realise they cannot live without self-exclusion or separation. This observation is helpful to reflect on the sticky nature of a patient's psyche, which fails to stabilise him/her in a sustainable way.

Solange nowadays tries to look for values on which she can rely to build herself back up. In particular, she believes in reincarnation, hoping that her psyche, her soul, can later be more serenely reborn in a body deserving respect and healing, and maintained by an environment that can lead her to fully integrate the process of personalisation, so well described by Winnicott (1971). This personal quest through her writing skills, a supporting cultural object, can be seen as underlining a movement towards another imprisonment whose ultimate objective is that of enduring the pain of having to witness the death of her relatives, at the same time absent but always present, trapped in her whole being, forever.

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